

IMPROVEMENT OF PARTICLE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES BY METAL FORMING AIDED BY CYCLIC SHEAR STRESS

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ABSTRACT

There are numerous defects that can be found in cast metal composites, such as pores, voids as well as nonhomogenous location, sedimentation and agglomeration of homophase and hetherophase reinforcement particles in a matrix of composite. Moreover, weak wetting of ceramic particles by liquid matrix material is the additional factor that contributes to worsening of properties of composite manufactured by classical casting processes. The paper presents a new method for altering the microstructure of cast composites reinforced with different kind of ceramic particles. The method consists in compression aided by additional shear stress caused by transverse motion of a punch. As the result, severe plastic deformation is possible without heat treatment between subsequent steps of plastic deformation. A series of experiments was conducted for previously casted Al-Mg-Cu matrix composites with three reinforcement variations. Silicon carbide particles, glassy carbon particles and the mixture of SiC particles and glassy carbon particles were used as the reinforcement. The mass percentage of reinforcement in every kind of composite was set to 15 wt%. It was found that the applied method allowed to eliminate the microstructure defects of initial as-cast microstructure. In addition, it enabled to refine the particles to the ultra-dispersed size with a good-quality conjunction on the particle-matrix interface and, in consequence to improve mechanical properties of the investigated composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, aluminum or aluminium-alloy based composites with ceramic particles as the reinforcement are frequently used in many fields of industry, e.g. automotive or aerospace [1, 2]. The particles of aluminum oxide, silicon carbide and silicon nitride are the most popular materials used as the reinforcement. Those materials create a homophases arrangement

of strengthening or a mixture of different types of particles, e.g. silicon carbide with graphite create heterophase reinforcement [3, 4]. The functional and mechanical properties of composite reinforced by particles depend on an percentage amount of reinforcing component in volume of composite and uniform distribution of this reinforcement in the matrix. One of the most popular technology of manufacturing composites reinforced by particles is a process that consists in stirring of particles with melted metal with subsequent casting the resulting suspension by gravity or mould casting [5, 6]. However, using casting method, the composite materials with many defects can be achieved. Among the most common problems observed during casting, the sedimentation of particles in consequence of differences in reinforcement and matrix densities and agglomerates creation during stirring, should be noted. Moreover, during crystallization, the front of solidification can lead to relocation of reinforcement particles, what multiply uneven distribution of particles in the volume of composite. The technology of stirring, similar to casting technology, lead to creating voids and pores of the casting, as a result of casting shrinkage or gassing of the liquid metal.

One of the method of avoiding defects obtained in casting process is a combination of metallurgical process with plastic deformation. The multistep technological processes of composites manufacturing are frequently conducted using powder metallurgy method with additional plastic deformation [6- 8]. The powder metallurgy processes ensure an uniform distribution of particles in the matrix powder, due to application of proper parameters of mechanical milling of components with subsequent pressing and sintering techniques. The obtained compacts are densified using plastic deformation at elevated temperature, like hot extrusion or hot forging. In consequence, the densification up to 95% of solid material can be achieved [7, 8].

The paper describes preliminary studies on improving properties of cast composites with ceramic particles by a forming method consisting in compression aided by additional shear stress that is caused by transverse, cyclic motion of a punch (Fig.1) [9,10].

Figure 1: A laboratory device for simultaneous compression aided by shear stress with transverse, cyclic motion of a punch: 1 - float guides, 2 - upper punch, 3 - sample, 4 - lower punch.

It was proved in a number of studies that metal forming methods aided by additional shear stress (eg. extrusion by KOBO method [11], rolling with transverse rolls motion [12], simultaneous compression with torsion [13]) cause severe plastic deformation of a workpiece. Moreover, the press load is significantly lower than the press load during conventional processes [14,15,16]. Thanks

to large deformation obtained in the presence of advantageous state of stress, this kind of forming allows to eliminate the defects of the initial as-cast microstructure and to obtain a homogenous, fine-grained and fine interphase microstructure. As a result, one can expect a significant improvement in mechanical properties of final products [17].

Composites containing ceramic particles are hard-to-form materials. This is due to both the presence of non-deformable ceramic particles and the weak bonding on the particle-matrix interface. The application of the proposed forming technology to process such composites would enable to block the slip systems on both the grain and phase boundaries and to improve both the strain-hardening of the matrix as well as hardening effect caused by introduction of ceramic particles to the matrix.

2 MATERIALS FOR INVESTIGATIONS

As a matrix of composite, the wrought alloy AlCu2SiMn, consisting of 2,2% Mg, 0,6% Cu, 0,7% Si, 1,2 Mn%, modified by 0.2% of strontium, was applied. The reinforcement phase, in amount of 15wt.%, consisted silicon carbide particles, glassy carbon particles or a mixture of silicon carbide with glassy carbon particles. In case of heterophase reinforcement, the 10wt.% of SiC and 5wt.% of amorphous carbon were used. The composites were produced by a method of stirring particles with melted metal, with subsequent gravity casting. The obtained composites were characterized by tensile strength at the level of tensile strength of matrix and very low strain to fracture (Tab. 1). In the structure of materials, a typical defects of casting process (Fig. 2), like relocation of particles in consequence of solidification front movement, particles agglomeration and poor bonding between phases (Fig.2a), were observed.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of investigated composites.

Material	Tensile strength, Rm, MPa	Elongation ϵ , %	Impact strength, J/mm ²
AlCu2SiMn +15% (SiC+WS)	95	5,8	7,7
AlCu2SiMn +15% SiC	115	7,5	10,2
AlCu2SiMn +15% WS	110	8,5	6,5

Figure 2: The microstructure of composites reinforced with SiC + GC particles after casting: a- particles segregation, b- bonding between components.

3 TESTING PROCEDURE

The aim of preliminary tests was to eliminate the defects of composites' initial as-cast microstructure by cold forming. The tests were performed on a unique laboratory device, enabling compression of samples simultaneously with transverse, cyclic motion of a punch (Fig. 1.). The cylindrical samples were used, of 25 mm both in height and in diameter. In order to secure the brittle samples from the threat of cracking in the early phase of the process, they were placed prior to deformation in steel sleeves of 25 mm in inner diameter, 25 mm in length and 4 mm in thickness. The compression velocity v was set to 0,2mm/s, while the amplitude A and frequency f of transverse punch motion was $\pm 0,5$ mm and 1Hz, respectively. Two reductions in height ε_t were taken into account: 50% and 33%.

4 ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Compressed samples were subjected to microstructural investigations. Changes of composite microstructure were observed in three different locations: at the sample midpoint, on the centerline in the area near the punch-sample interface and at the middle of the sample height, close to the lateral edge of the sample (nearby the steel sleeve-sample interface). The results revealed some differences of the composite microstructure that depend on the area of observation. Selected images of the SiC-reinforced composite microstructure are presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: The microstructure of composite reinforced with 15 wt. % SiC particles after 33% reduction in height; a-close to the punch, b-midpoint, c-close to the lateral edge, LM, mag.50x.

Similar changes in microstructure were observed in the samples with the heterophase reinforcement that consisted the mix of silicon carbide and glassy carbon particles (Fig.4) as well as in the composite reinforced with the homophase of glassy carbon.

Figure 4: Microstructure of composite reinforced with 15 wt. % SiC +GC particles after 33% reduction in height; a-close to the punch, b-midpoint, c-close to the lateral edge, LM, mag.50x.

The character of deformation depends on a sample area. In the central part of the sample one can find strain-hardened matrix areas with band structure of particles and with shear bands on matrix grain boundaries. It is particularly observed in the area near the lateral edge of the sample. There were

no such significant changes of the composite microstructure in the area located close to the punch-sample interface.

Application of 33% reduction in height during compression with transverse, cyclic punch motion permits to obtain good interphase bonding and to eliminate porosity. The increase of reduction in height to 50% increases strain-hardening effect in the central part of the sample. It is accompanied with microstructure texturing (Fig.5).

Figure 5: The strain-hardened microstructure of composite reinforced with SiC (a) and composite reinforced with SiC+GS particles after 50% reduction in height; a-close to the punch, b-midpoint, c-close to the lateral edge, LM, a- mag.100x, b-mag.200x.

High stress that occurs during simultaneous compression with cyclic transverse punch motion causes also cracking and refining of the reinforcement particles. This effect can be observed in the composite reinforced with hard, non-formable silicon carbide particles. However, refined particles are quite well bonded with matrix which is able to fill just-created interphase areas, especially in the case of larger deformation (Fig.6).

Figure 6: The SiC particles fragmentation in composite after plastic deformation 33% (a) and -50% (b), LM, mag. 200x.

The particle refinement is related to their elastic properties. It can be more often observed in SiC particles than in glassy carbon (Fig.7). Glassy carbon and silicon carbide particles exhibit comparable hardness (6-7 in the Mohs scale) but significantly different elastic modulus (for SiC it is approx. 260

GPa and for glassy carbon it's about 30 GPa) [18-19]. High stress in the central part of composite can cause even very significant refinement of reinforcing particles. Ultrafine particles are bonded very well with the composite matrix (Fig. 8). Thus, it would contribute to the increase of mechanical and tribological properties of the composite [20, 21].

Figure 7: The particles fragmentation in composite reinforced with SiC + GC after 50% reduction in height, LM, mag. 200x.

Figure 8: The particles fragmentation in composite reinforced SiC after 50% reduction in height, LM, mag. 200x.

5 SUMMARY

The aim of the conducted studies was to evaluate the opportunity of processing cast composites reinforced with ceramic particles by cold metal forming in order to eliminate typical defects of the as-cast microstructure and to improve their mechanical properties. A choice of the forming process – compression with simultaneous transverse, cyclic motion of the punch – was driven by the opportunity to intensify significantly plastic deformation by means of the additional shear stress induced in the samples. The effective strain obtained in the compressed samples was several times larger than the strain to fracture in the static tensile test.

The preliminary tests already proved that it is possible with this method to obtain conditions necessary for elimination of casting defects that occur in composites made by mixing of ceramic particles with a liquid metal matrix. The results of microstructural investigations suggest that the applied method has a great potential for improving microstructure and properties of composite materials. It was found that the composite obtained after the proposed forming process was dense and exhibited good microstructural homogeneity, uniform distribution of ceramic particles and no voids were observed as well. One can expect that compression aided by additional shear stress would allow for considerable strain-hardening of a matrix material, improvement of boundary bonding, and in consequence to improve mechanical properties of the investigated composites.

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